

Augmented Reality Platform to Support Human-Robot Bi-Directional Interaction

Graziano Carriero, Nicolas Calzone, Monica Sileo, Rocco Mozzillo, Francesco Pierri, Fabrizio Caccavale

School of Engineering
University of Basilicata
Potenza, Italy
graziano.carriero@unibas.it

Abstract—This work introduces an Augmented Reality application designed for HoloLens 2, aiming at facilitating the interaction between collaborative robots and human operators, regardless of their robotics knowledge and experience. The proposed application allows bi-directional data exchange between the robot and the human operator. In particular, the robot provides information on its state, in terms of joints and workspace data, while the human operator can generate and manipulate the desired end-effector trajectory in real-time.

Index Terms—Mixed Reality, Robotics, Human-Robot Interaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic idea of the Industry 4.0 paradigm is the development of autonomous technologies, where the robots closely collaborate with human operators [1], [2]. An essential aspect of the collaborative robotics is the exchange of information, which can take two forms: *unidirectional communication*, where one agent (the collaborative robot, called cobot, or the operator) communicates with the other one, and *bi-directional communication*, where a two-way information flow is established. For example, effective bi-directional communication can enhance user perceptions of the robot reliability and, at the same time, makes her/him able to provide instructions and commands to the cobot.

The development of effective bidirectional Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) can be achieved through the implementation of interfaces that can allow low-skilled operators to easily interact with cobots. Some of these interfaces exploit Augmented Reality (AR) or Mixed Reality (MR) environments in order to improve human's performance. In [3], visual feedback is used through Microsoft HoloLens devices to supply the task force in a collaborative polishing, while acoustic feedback is exploited when the cobot hologram is out of the user's sight.

II. PROPOSED PLATFORM

An AR application, specifically designed for HoloLens 2 [4], is proposed in this work, built on the previous one presented in [5]. The proposed platform enables the human operator to interact with the cobot by providing inputs and commands, and, simultaneously, to exchange data with it.

In detail, the human operator visualizes in real-time the information concerning the cobot's state and its workspace. In addition, she/he can assign a trajectory to the cobot's end-effector by physically manipulating its holographic twin in

(a) Validation of calibration procedure.

(b) Virtual joint spheres.

Fig. 1: Snapshots of the calibration procedure and of the robot state visualization.

the AR environment. The planned trajectory is shown in the environment, as a series of way-points, so that the operator can validate it before sending it to the cobot or she/he can suitably adjust it by dragging a subset of them.

III. MIXED REALITY FEATURES

The application Main Menu panel provides access to the real-time numerical data of the cobot, i.e. joints' positions, velocities and torques, and to the HRC Simulation Control Panel, which provides the human-robot interaction features, detailed in the following sections.

A. Calibration

A calibration procedure is required to align the virtual model of the cobot to the real one in the AR environment. An algorithm has been developed to assess the accuracy of this method. It exploits two QR codes, placed in a fixed and known position in the real world: the first one is employed to collocate the cobot hologram in the AR environment, while the second one is used to estimate any calibration errors in both position and orientation (see Fig. 1a).

Let \mathbf{d}_{qr} be the relative position and orientation (in terms of Euler angles) vector between the two coordinate frames attached to the top left corner of the two QR codes in the real world, whereas $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_{qr}$ represents the corresponding vector in the AR environment. The latter coordinate frames are provided by the QR code detection algorithm of HoloLens 2.

Fig. 2: Robot workspace.

Thus, the calibration errors can be straightforwardly calculated as $e = \mathbf{d}_{qr} - \hat{\mathbf{d}}_{qr}$.

Once the hologram is collocated in the AR environment, a panel appears showing the position errors in *meters*, and the orientation errors expressed in *degrees*. Then, the operator can validate the calibration results, by using a *Yes/No* button; in case of rejection, the procedure has to be repeated.

B. Robot state

During the interaction with the cobot, e.g. in hand-guiding tasks, the operator might find it useful to visualize the distance between the current positions of the joints and their limits. In the proposed application, a virtual sphere for each joint is displayed aligned with the corresponding real joint, as shown in Fig. 1b. The color of each sphere changes according to how far the current position of the joint is from the limit. A colormap (green, yellow and red) is used to denote three levels of proximity (far, near, close).

C. Robot workspace visualization

In the definition of some tasks, it can be useful to know what are the 3D points that are reachable by the end-effector, e.g. when the operator needs to place an object to be manipulated or when she/he has to set the final position of a cobot motion. To this aim, the application allows to show the cobot workspace in the AR environment through a green surface (see Fig. 2). Moreover, if the operator sets a final end-effector position outside the achievable space, the workspace is highlighted in red.

D. Trajectory generation

When the target pose of the end-effector is correctly assigned, the application plans a linear motion by using a fifth-order polynomial function. The way-points of the trajectory are shown to the operator through a series of spheres, as shown in Fig. 3a, where the last sphere corresponds to the pose previously defined by the operator.

E. Trajectory validation and execution

In some particular cases, e.g. to avoid obstacles, the operator can easily interact with some way-points, i.e. the orange ones,

(a) Possible obstacle collision.

(b) Modified trajectory around the obstacle.

Fig. 3: Trajectory modification in the presence of an obstacle.

displayed in the AR environment. The new positions of these way-points are used to compute a cubic interpolating spline to define the new path. An example of the trajectory validation can be seen in Fig. 3b. At this point, if the trajectory is approved, the operator can command the robot to execute the desired motion.

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